

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The elderly are on the rise, a university problem that grows every day

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Abstract

God forgives, but time to none, says the song. What a profound truth! Sometimes part of the intellect is preserved, but other times it is lost forever. The above when detecting any psychoanalytic or neurological abnormality in the patient. In what age range do these symptoms appear? It is not 100% clear, cases have even been detected in people under 50 years of age. What do countries do in these cases? In Chile there are clubs for older adults that take advantage of some government royalties, offering special trips to see places other than the country of origin. Is that waiting for us? At the University, monetary stimuli are offered to all those who have reached enough age to leave the institution and light the fireplace, understanding by the latter the incorporation of new academics from some fashionable professions, but one thing is clear, everything with the doctor degree at least.

Keywords: Elderly; Monetary stimuli; Alzheimer; Neurological abnormalities; Death

1. Introduction

Cognitive impairment is a very important component in the transmission of knowledge from teacher to student. The law of life indicates that there would be an age range in which people must leave their jobs if these adverse conditions appear and retirement –at least in Chile- is not a solution that leaves no one alone. Due to the above, in the field of public service (the university is sometimes public) some royalties or incentives have been offered, both academic and non-academic staff. However, some who achieve that stimulus also continue to take classes after the age of 70 [1].

All of the above can be considered legally and ethically correct if there are adequate synapses in the successful ones, but this will not always be the case. The above in knowledge of the existence of cognitive alterations such as Alzheimer's disease and other similar ones that must be considered and not hidden among friends [2]. On the other hand, if there were no alterations of that type, the correct thing to do would be to accept that retirement is a certain but monetarily insufficient alternative. For example, when considering the university hierarchies at our University, it is not at all attractive to retire at 65, the legal age in Chile for men and 60 for women. Therefore, these royalties (retirement incentive) do not stop being for those who are around that age [3].

God forgives but time none, sang Juan Gabriel [4]. It is a deep and cracked truth. Cracks in the life of any of us, both for the one who writes it, for the one who publishes it and also for the one who reviews it and accepts it for publication. This is as important and ethical as the best work published in the best WoS journal. Not accepting it is like contradicting the fact that Kary Mullis' brilliant idea did not separate the waters in Molecular Medicine, that is, in a before and after PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction) [5,6].

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2. Material and methods

In general, and our universities do not escape this, workers dedicate their lives to their work. In all professions such as Biochemistry, Medicine, Law, Chemistry and Pharmacy, Dentistry, Journalism, and many others, there are senior academics. I met quite a few when I served at the Clinical Hospital of the University of Chile, a place where there are doctors of all ages, but none to that date with symptoms like those mentioned. Thus, it is not a bad idea that in our country the retirement of those who should already leave is encouraged and thus give way to young people, a necessary replacement [3,7].

In other cases, the elderly are also on retreat in their barracks, priests and professionals from the forces of order and security are examples of this. Although the latter can resume some labor remuneration upon retirement based on years of service and not age. Anyway, retirement should be considered as something that has a complement when deciding: the retirement incentive, which in our country is around 40 thousand dollars [8].

Specifically, what can a retired academic do? Not much. Your income decreases more or less in half, but you can join a Senior Adult Group and dedicate yourself to traveling, for example. Or it can be assigned to a Painting or Dance Workshop, until a symptom appears as the main or typical of osteoarthritis. Without naming deafness yet.

Nothing is free in the end, and how would all this be more bearable? If we all knew that we have an old man on us, as Serrat says...![9].

3. Discussion

Although climate change has not been incorporated into this article, *we talk so much about leaving a better planet to our kids, that we forget about leaving better kids to our planet* [10]. Children who worry or care about the ailments of their elders: their parents and grandparents. And what about associated health systems?

Today there is no real awareness of all this and when you are old, it is too late. What is important now in our universities? Publish in highly renowned journals and encourage the intrinsic individualism of each one? Aging is the law of life and no one is exempt.

Obviously, those who do not suffer from Alzheimer's will be able to rejoice with the achievements obtained throughout their academic career, understanding by these their WoS publications or their successful as an academic at a university. Those who suffer from Alzheimer's or something similar will never remember it. And what is worse, those who were part of a commission that evaluated the background of other academics and did wrong, will not remember it either [11].

4. Conclusion

Humans are the worst animal species that exists and when you get old everything seems far away and no door opens around you. Unfortunately young people believe they are immortal, just as we believed ourselves.

Compliance with ethical standards

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To all those who have read this article and make it viral

Disclosure of conflict of interest

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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